

D3.1 Report on optimising collection and logistics of plastic waste, and boosting recycling plastics and uptake of products made from recycled plastics

WP no and title: WP3 KVC-DEMOS: Circular plastics value chain
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This document contains the D3.1 Report on optimising collection and logistics of plastic waste, and boosting recycling plastics and uptake of products made from recycled plastics for the TREASoURcE project (Grant Agreement No. 101059491).

Project Details			
Project acronym	TREASoURcE	Start / Duration	June 2022 / 48 months
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-01 – Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)'s circular systemic solutions	Grant Agreement No	101059491
Type of Action	Innovation Action (IA)	Coordinator	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
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Website	https://treasource.eu		

Deliverable Details			
Deliverable No	D3.1		
Deliverable Name	Report on optimising collection and logistics of plastic waste, and boosting recycling plastics and uptake of products made from recycled plastics		
Work Package	3		
Dissemination level	SEN/PU	Type	Report
Due Date (M)	23	Submission date	M28
Lead Beneficiary	SINTEF	Responsible Author	Stephan Kubowicz

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Document History			
Date	Version	Name	Changes
17/06/2024	0.1	Stephan Kubowicz	First draft
08/07/2024	0.2	Stephan Kubowicz	Second draft
30/09/2024	1.0	Ugur Kaya	Reviewed and final version

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
ABS	Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene
CBM	Circular business model
CDW	Construction and demolition waste
D	Deliverable
DRS	Deposit return system
DSC	Differential scanning calorimetry
EEA	European Environment Agency
EKOF	Ekokumppanit Oy (EcoFellows)
ELV	End-of-life vehicle
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
EU	European Union
EV	Electric vehicle
EVA	Ethylene-vinyl acetate
EVOH	Ethylene-vinyl alcohol
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
KVC	Key value chain
KVC-DEMO	Key value chain demonstration
LDPE	Low-density polyethylene
LLDPE	Linear low-density polyethylene
MFI	Melt Flow Index
MSW	Municipal solid waste
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners
NCS	National collection schemes
PA	Polyamide
PC	Polycarbonate
PCR	Post-consumer recycle
PE	Polyethylene
PEN	Polyethylene naphthalate
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PIR	Post-industrial recycle
PMMA	Polymethyl methacrylate
PP	Polypropylene
PPWD	Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive
PS	Polystyrene
PU	Polyurethane

PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
SE	Stakeholder engagement
SE-DEMO	Stakeholder engagement demonstration
SINTEF	SINTEF AS / SINTEF Energy
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
WEEE	Waste from electronics and electrical equipment
XRF	X-ray fluorescence analysis

Executive Summary

This deliverable report is part of Work Package 3, KVC-Demos: Circular plastics value chain and outlines a comprehensive approach to enhancing the recycling and reuse of non-circulated plastic waste streams. TREASoURcE EU-project aims to initiate systemic change by developing systemic circular economy solutions in cities and regions for currently underutilised or unused plastic waste streams to support the market development of recycled plastics through mechanical and thermochemical recycling.

Circular economy initiatives can drive economic growth by creating jobs in waste collection, recycling, and manufacturing with recycled materials but transitioning to a circular economy for plastics is complex. Efforts to increase plastic value chain circularity are driven by regulatory pressure, organizational commitment, and industry competition and collaboration. This report provides an in-depth overview of the current state of the circular economy for plastics within the EU and Nordic countries, highlighting critical areas such as optimized collection and logistics, boosting recycling rates, and increasing the use of recycled plastics in new products.

The project focuses on various application areas such as agricultural plastics, post-consumer packaging waste, and industrial plastic waste streams. After identifying these waste streams, the next step involved optimizing collection, logistics, and pretreatment processes to ensure efficient recycling. The report includes numerous results, practical applications, and key learnings from circular plastics demonstrations, offering a roadmap for advancing the circular economy of plastics in the Nordic regions.

Proper collection and sorting are essential for better recycling output for both mechanical and chemical recycling. However, many solutions for improving collection and sorting remain unimplemented due to cost concerns, resulting in the loss of valuable plastic waste materials. Furthermore, a significant barrier to the recyclability and increased recycled content of plastic products is their complex design, including the use of composites and multi-layer packaging. Promoting eco-design with mono-material, single-layer solutions, and design for disassembly should be integrated into procurement procedures to boost demand for recyclable and reusable products. Specifications for relevant products and plastic types must ensure recyclability. In addition, Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), as an environmental policy, makes producers responsible for their products' end-of-life management, shifting waste management costs from local governments to the industry and encouraging more recyclable products.

An effective strategy to improve plastic management and increase plastic value chain circularity includes also raising awareness about proper plastic handling and measuring the effects of these efforts to guide future initiatives.

1 INTRODUCTION

Climate change, environmental degradation, and loss of biodiversity are major global threats requiring urgent collaborative actions across industries, sectors, cities and regions, communities, and citizens. Half of total greenhouse gas emissions and more than 90% of biodiversity losses stem from resource extraction and processing. Global consumption of materials, especially biomass, fossil fuels, metals, and minerals, is expected to double by 2060, and annual waste generation is estimated to increase by 70% by 2050 (Oberle, 2019).

TREASoURcE EU-project aims to initiate systemic change by developing systemic circular economy solutions in cities and regions for currently underutilised or unused plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries, and bio-based waste and side streams. Implementing these solutions in collaboration with companies, societies (including citizens, consumers, communities, and regional actors) and experts is expected to significantly increase product and material circulation in the Nordic and Baltic Sea Regions.

This report is part of Work Package 3, KVC-Demos: Circular plastics value chain, and outlines a comprehensive approach to enhancing the recycling and reuse of currently non-circulated plastic waste streams. The project aims to create added-value products from these waste streams to support the market development of recycled plastics and capture the value lost today by utilizing mechanical and thermochemical recycling.

Plastics are used in a multitude of applications; therefore, our project focuses on various application areas: agricultural plastics, post-consumer packaging waste recycling rejects, industrial plastic waste streams, and plastic foil from shredded EV batteries. Once these waste streams were identified, the next step involved locking in possibilities for optimizing the collection, logistics, and pretreatment processes to ensure efficient recycling.

Following this, a thorough analysis of the feedstock was conducted, and mechanical recycling experiments performed to determine the viability of mechanical and chemical recycling methods. A critical part of this process was identifying the best route for recycling - whether mechanical or chemical - based on the characteristics of the waste and the desired outcomes.

Finally, promoting the use of recycled plastics in products is essential to close the loop in the circular economy. By increasing the market demand for recycled plastics, we can support the development of a sustainable system that reduces waste and conserves resources.

2 Overview of circular economy of plastics in the EU

The EU's strategy for plastics, adopted in 2018, is part of the broader Circular Economy Action Plan. It addresses the challenges posed by plastic waste and seeks to enhance the recyclability of plastic packaging, reduce single-use plastics, and tackle microplastic pollution. The strategy also includes measures to modernize EU waste legislation, reflecting the urgency to mitigate the negative impacts of plastics on marine ecosystems, biodiversity, and human health. The circular economy of plastics in the EU is a transformative approach to rethinking the lifecycle of plastics, aiming to keep materials in use for as long as possible and to minimize waste. This concept is a cornerstone of the EU's strategy to transition towards a carbon-neutral and sustainable economy.

The European Environment Agency has highlighted the environmental concerns associated with plastics, emphasizing the need for improved waste management and reduction of marine litter. The EEA has published several reports that provide insights into the role of plastics in Europe, the assessment of marine litter, the management of non-packaging plastics, and the pathways towards circular plastics. These publications underscore the importance of transitioning from a linear, fossil-fuel-based system to a circular plastics economy. They also evaluate the evolution of the circular economy of plastics in the EU, comparing current data with previous years to measure progress.

The circular economy of plastics in the EU is an evolving framework that seeks to address the complex challenges of plastic waste through innovation, policymaking, and collaboration across the value chain. The transition to a circular model is underway, with steps made in increasing the use of recycled plastics and slowly reducing the reliance on virgin materials. The EU's commitment to this transition is evident in its strategic plans and the ongoing research and innovation efforts to achieve a sustainable plastics economy.

Challenges identified across the plastic value chain highlight its scale and complexity of transforming from linear to circular plastics. Specifically for recycling, these challenges include issues related to feedstock acquisition and quality, sorting, identification and recycling technologies, the uptake of recycled plastic, and the regulatory environment. There is no single technology or solution to address all the challenges related to transitioning to a circular economy for plastics. Instead, joint actions across the entire value chain - including manufacturers, consumers, recyclers, and policymakers - are necessary (Tenhunen, 2020). The responsibilities and reporting obligations of companies, organizations, and public institutions are increasing. Utilizing circular economy plastics can help meet these obligations. Additionally, the use of recycled materials can provide an advantage in procurement evaluations.

2.1 Plastics use and waste feedstocks

Achieving circularity for plastics is a complex endeavour. Currently, there are thousands of different types of plastics, each with various applications. In Europe, packaging represents the primary use of plastics (40.5%), followed by buildings and construction (20.4%), the automotive sector (8.8%), waste from electronics and electrical equipment (WEEE) (6.2%), household, leisure, and sports (4.3%), and

agriculture (3.2%) (Plastics Europe, 2021). The diversity in plastic applications means there is no single collection or recycling strategy, nor a unified circular business model that can address the circularity problem of plastics comprehensively.

Moreover, the addition of harmful or toxic additives makes recycling even more challenging. Precise control and separation of waste flow into recycling plants are needed to ensure safety and maintain the quality of recycled products, which some additives may compromise. These products often originate from construction and demolition, automotive, or WEEE sectors.

2.1.1 Europe

In 2021, Europe produced 57.2 million tonnes of plastic . According to Eurostat data , plastic was primarily used for packaging (40%), followed by consumer and household goods (22%), and buildings and construction (20%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Plastic production and plastic waste treatment in EU in 2015

As a result of plastic production and consumption, Europe generates approximately 25.8 million tonnes of plastic waste annually. Of which, the dominant waste generation is from the packaging sector reaching at 59%, followed by other streams with less than 10% contribution such as EEE, agriculture and automotive (Figure 2). Less than 30% of this waste is collected for recycling, with a significant portion sent to non-EU countries for treatment, often under different environmental standards. Meanwhile, the rates of landfilling and incineration of plastic waste remain high at 31% and 39%, respectively. Although landfilling has decreased over the past decade, incineration has increased (Figure 1).

EU PLASTIC WASTE GENERATION IN 2015

Figure 2. Plastic waste generation by types in 2015

Half of the plastic collected for recycling in the EU is exported to countries outside the EU due to insufficient capacity, technology, or financial resources for local treatment. Previously, a significant portion of plastic waste exports went to China, but recent import restrictions to non-OECD countries are expected to reduce EU exports, potentially increasing incineration and landfilling of plastic waste in Europe. In addition, the EU's low plastic recycling rate may result in significant economic and environmental losses. In 2019, around 22 million tonnes of plastic ended up in soils, rivers, and oceans, with projections estimating that plastic leakage will double by 2060.

Consequently, promoting plastic circular economy has been one of the EU key strategies for sustainable development. Plastic recycling in current practices face several challenges including the quality and cost of recycled products compared to virgin materials. Plastic processors need large quantities of recycled plastic that meet strict specifications at competitive prices. However, the customization of plastics to meet specific functional or aesthetic needs complicates the recycling process, making it more costly and affecting the quality of recycled products.

2.1.2 Nordics

According to the report by the Nordic Council on plastic waste markets in the Nordics (2018), the Nordic countries Iceland, Norway, Sweden, Finland and Denmark generate approximately 1 million tonnes of plastic waste on an annual basis. Figure 3 depicts the share of different plastic waste

feedstocks and country level generation of waste; packaging waste is the largest source of post-consumer plastic waste, with over 700,000 tonnes generated annually in the Nordic region, and other waste streams, including municipal solid waste (MSW), agricultural waste, waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), end-of-life vehicles (ELVs), and construction and demolition (C&D) waste, together contribute about 270,000 tonnes of plastics. Some waste streams like agriculture, ELVs, and C&D typically have fewer types of plastics, making them potentially more suitable for recycling. In contrast, MSW and WEEE contain a wider variety of plastics.

Note: The Eurostat data for Finnish agricultural plastic waste varies significantly from year to year. The figure from 10,000 tonnes to nearly 0.

Figure 3. Amount of plastic waste generated per waste stream in the Nordic region in 2018

Plastics are used in a multitude of applications; therefore, the TREASoURcE project focuses on various application areas: agricultural plastics, post-consumer packaging waste recycling rejects, industrial plastic waste streams, and so on. The complexity of plastic waste streams arises from the wide range of different polymers used in different applications demanding different types of properties and functionalities. The products are in many cases a combination of different polymers and components. This poses specific requirements for plastic recycling. Mixing different types of products and polymers together lowers the quality of recycled products, as it is hard to separate and process them properly.

To get high-quality recycled materials, it is important to carefully sort each type of plastic, which is challenging given the variety and combination of plastics in waste.

McKinnon et al. (2018) combined the data from Eurostat and Hestin et al (2015) and depicted the distribution of different types of polymers seen in different plastic waste stream categories. While other waste streams are dominated by a few main types of polymers, packaging waste includes a wide variety of plastic polymers.

Figure 4. Plastic types in each plastic waste stream in the Nordic countries (McKinnon et al. 2018).

Feedstock material diversity and heterogeneity as well as contamination and impurities of the feedstocks have been described as bottlenecks and technical barriers. Also, specific to the Nordics are the following technical barriers; low volumes and fluctuating supply of plastic waste, and lack of treating and sorting. As the quality of the feedstock material is determinative for high-quality recycling, smart collection and efficient pre-treatment methods are critical to improve circularity of plastics in the Nordics.

2.2 Collection

For a circular economy, efficient waste collection is a fundamental first step toward effective recycling. Properly collecting and separating waste enhances recycling efficiency and increases the quality and quantity of recyclates. Effective waste collection significantly influences waste streams and their

suitability for downstream pre-treatment, sorting, recycling, and recovery operations. Ideally, a harmonized process for waste management, collection, and separation should be implemented across the value chain, from waste collection and management companies to municipal and commercial operations. The EU's Waste Framework Directive outlines the basic requirements and concepts for waste management, setting forth two important elements that affect plastic waste collection (Plastics Europe, 2024):

- 'Polluter pays principle'
- Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)

2.2.1 Municipal household plastic waste

In the EU, post-consumer plastic waste is typically collected via curb side pickup, permanent drop-off collection points, deposit-return points, or special collections. Single-stream recycling is one method where various recyclable materials such as plastic, glass, paper, and aluminium are combined in a single bag or container. While this mixed collection method reduces collection costs, it has significant drawbacks. These include lower quality recycled material due to contamination and increased sorting costs. An alternative method is separate collection, where all recyclable materials are collected individually. This results in a more homogeneous waste stream for recyclers. The more homogeneous the stream, the easier it is to sort. It also reduces contamination from other materials, thereby producing higher-quality recycled material (BCC Research, 2022).

2.2.2 Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment plastics

The collection of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) are managed through various methods such as designated collection facilities, kerbside collection, bulky waste collections, and retailer take-back program. Designated collection facilities are typically run by local authorities or their contractors, though distributors, retailers, producers, charities, and social enterprises may also manage these sites. Designated collection facilities must have the necessary permits and ensure proper separation of WEEE. Kerbside collection is where people can place WEEE items in designated bins or bags for collection alongside regular household waste. Bulky waste collection can allow people to schedule pickups for large appliances or electronics, and retailer take-back programs enable customers to return old items to stores for proper disposal or recycling when purchasing new product. Recycling facilities then process collected WEEE and sell the sorted materials to refining and manufacturing industries.

The most important materials in terms of volume are steel, aluminium, copper, and plastics. Separating plastics from WEEE can be done manually without difficulties. The result, however, is a fraction of mixed plastics parts, including many different plastic types of which some contain undesirable additives (e.g., flame retardants). This makes the further processing and valorisation of this plastic fraction more challenging due to the need to sort different types of plastics and remove those containing hazardous additives.

2.2.3 End-of-Life Vehicle plastics

The End-of-Life Vehicle (ELV) Directive outlines a structured process for the collection and disposal of ELVs. Owners are required to bring their end-of-life vehicles to new or used car dealers, who then send the ELVs to authorized collectors or dismantlers. Car owners must obtain a certificate of destruction from either the car dealer or an authorized facility to deregister the vehicle, with requirements varying by country. Authorized dismantlers and collectors remove reusable parts such as engines, gearboxes, body parts, and airbags for resale, and depollute ELVs by safely removing batteries, air conditioner fluids, and oils. They handle special waste and conduct thorough separation to reduce subsequent waste. Shredders further dismantle the remaining car parts and shred the car body, separating metal components for recycling and creating automobile shredder residue (ASR) from non-metal items like fabric, paper, wood, plastic, and rubber. Combustible parts of ASR are used as alternative fuels in industrial processes such as cement production. The remaining ASR, after energy recovery, is landfilled.

Plastics make up 12% to 16% of a vehicle's total weight, hence, their efficient recovery and recycling could significantly improve the existing EU Plastics Strategy . The management schemes for ELV plastics (ELVP), are complex and lack harmonization across countries. These schemes generally include dismantling (depollution) and shredding, post-shredding treatment is not commonly practiced despite being commercially available. Instead, non-metal fractions like plastics are usually sent directly to energy recovery for two main reasons. First, ELVPs are highly commingled with other fractions, making their recovery technically feasible only after a series of complex sorting steps. Secondly, conventional mechanical recycling cannot recover the various polymers used in ELVP due to the presence of additives such as brominated flame retardants, plasticisers, stabilisers (including heavy metals), glass fibres, and contaminants like volatile organic compounds, fuels and oil residues.

2.2.4 Construction and demolition waste plastics

Construction and demolition waste (CDW) accounts for more than a third of all waste generated in the EU. According to the EU Construction & Demolition Waste Management Protocol, effective CDW management begins with identifying, separating and collecting CDW at the source. This process relies on clear definitions, quality pre-demolition audits, and well-executed waste management plans. Key elements include eliminating hazardous waste and separating materials that hinder recycling, such as fixation materials. Additionally, improved collection for reuse and recycling requires selective demolition and proper on-site operations.

Of all CDW, the fraction of plastic waste is only a small 1%, but they make a significant contribution to a huge variety of construction applications. The source separation, collection and recycling plastics from CDW faces significant obstacles. These include the high cost, time, and space needed for dismantling and separation, especially in urban areas. Additionally, there is a lack of synergy between authorities and the private sector, and the low cost and poor regulation of landfilling reduce incentives

for recycling. Insufficient sorting and crushing plants, along with cross-contamination and mixing of materials, further complicate the recycling process.

2.2.5 Agricultural plastics

The growing use of plastics in agriculture has significantly benefited farmers. Various types of plastics, including polyolefins like polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer (EVA), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polycarbonate (PC), and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), are utilized in agriculture applications. Plastics enable year-round cultivation of fruits and vegetables, improve water conservation, maintain temperature, and enhance crop quality. They also reduce pesticide use by protecting crops in greenhouses or under plastic films and help retain rainwater in reservoirs, making cultivation in arid areas possible. (Plastics Europe, 2021)

Farmers need to manage significant plastic waste as on-farm burning, or burial is forbidden in most countries. Agricultural plastic waste must be collected and transported to treatment facilities, often through national or local collection schemes. However, this process adds to farmers' workloads, as plastic waste must be stored in dry, secure locations to prevent contamination and environmental pollution. Removing plastic debris is labour-intensive, and improper handling can lead to environmental contamination.

The management of agricultural plastic waste in Europe involves National Collection Schemes (NCS) to promote a circular economy and reduce environmental impact. NCS ensures high collection rates and better quality of collected plastic waste, which is crucial for effective recycling and incorporating recycled materials into new products. These schemes operate in countries like France, Germany, Finland, and Ireland, and are beginning in the UK and Spain. NCS relies on extended producer responsibility, shared by converters, farmers, distributors, and other stakeholders. The cost of recycling new plastic is covered by an eco-contribution added to the sales price. Once collected from the fields, plastics are cleaned to remove sand, herbs, and pesticides, then ground and extruded into pellets for manufacturing new products. When mechanical recycling is not feasible, alternative methods like chemical recycling and energy recovery are used for efficient waste management. (Plastics Europe, 2021)

2.3 Pre-treatment technologies

Given the complexity of plastic waste streams, pre-treatment is a prerequisite for both mechanical and chemical recycling. This complexity arises from the mixture of various plastics, contaminants, additives, and the bulky nature of plastic waste. It's important to note that the quality of the recyclate is directly proportional to the quality of the feedstock. This underscores the importance of pre-treatment, making it as crucial as the recycling process itself. Currently, a range of pre-treatment methods are in use, from traditional approaches like sorting and washing to more advanced techniques. However,

these methods fall short in thoroughly cleaning and removing impurities from the plastic waste stream (Kol, 2021).

The source of plastic waste, such as post-consumer plastic or construction waste, significantly influences the types of contaminants present in the waste stream. Consequently, procedures like sorting, screening, washing, and shredding may be executed in varying sequences, repeated multiple times, or even omitted entirely for a particular waste stream (Ragaert, 2017).

2.3.1 Sorting

Sorting processes typically rely on characteristics such as size, shape, density, colour, or chemical composition, and are often carried out in a sequence of steps (Lange, 2021) (Ragaert, 2017). Commonly used sorting methods include waste screening, air separation, ballistic separation, magnetic separation, eddy current separation, sensor-based sorting, and to a certain extent, manual sorting (Kol, 2021). However, the field is continuously evolving, with promising technologies like watermarking and barcoding being explored to improve plastic sorting.

Sorting on size is typically done manually or by using sieves. Plastics can be distinguished from other materials like metal and glass through a variety of methods. Common methods are the use of gravity in airflow or density-based separation in water. However, metals can also be removed efficiently by magnetic separators utilizing magnetic attraction of ferrous metal.

Automated sorting of plastic waste employs advanced technologies such as infrared sensors, optical sorters, and machine learning algorithms to identify and separate different types of plastics. This method is highly efficient, capable of processing large volumes of waste in a short time and reduces the risk of human exposure to hazardous materials. On the other hand, manual sorting involves individuals physically separating plastic waste. While this method can be more accurate in distinguishing subtle differences between plastic types, it is labour-intensive, time-consuming, and exposes workers to potential health risks. Therefore, while manual sorting may be suitable for smaller-scale operations or specific types of waste, automated sorting is generally more efficient and safer for large-scale plastic recycling processes and is mainly applied for post-consumer plastic waste in municipalities.

However, implementing automated sorting for plastic waste also presents challenges, such as:

- **Complexity of Plastic Waste:** Automated sorting equipment is typically designed to sort single-component materials. However, sorting of film, multilayered, blended, or mixed-material plastics is problematic (Lubongo C, 2022).
- **Cost:** The initial investment for automated sorting technologies can be high, and the ongoing maintenance costs can also be significant.

2.3.2 Sink-float density separation

Certain types of plastics can be effectively separated from one another by leveraging their distinct differences in density. For instance, polyolefins, a category of plastics that includes polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP), typically have a density of approximately 0.9 g/cm^3 . On the other hand, plastics such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) have a higher density, around 1.4 g/cm^3 . This difference in density provides a straightforward method for separating lighter plastics, such as PE and PP, from heavier ones like PVC and PET. The process involves subjecting the mixed plastics to a medium (often water) with a specific density. The lighter plastics float, while the heavier ones sink, allowing for easy separation. This method of separation is commonly employed in various industries, including agricultural and manufacturing sectors, where large volumes of plastic waste are generated. During the separation process also contaminants such as soil or stones are effectively removed.

2.3.3 Washing

Cleaning plastic waste is not only essential for mechanical recycling but also greatly advantageous for chemical recycling. Contaminants and dirt can often hinder the reprocessing, making even well-sorted plastic unsuitable for reprocessing without washing. The cleaning process typically involves water and can be enhanced by caustic agents or detergents. The washing unit is usually integrated into the sink-float sorting step following size reduction. The purification step is relatively costly, necessitating washing and drying equipment, as well as wastewater treatment. Furthermore, even the most efficient washing methods do not entirely remove odorous components, even with a caustic wash. Nonpolar components require an additional detergent or organic solvent for more efficient removal, necessitating an effective wastewater treatment unit (Lange, 2021).

2.4 Recycling technologies

2.4.1 Mechanical recycling

Mechanical recycling of plastics involves the process of sorting, cleaning, and reprocessing used plastic materials into new products. Plastic waste is collected and typically sorted based on type and quality. This step ensures that only compatible plastics are processed together. The sorted plastic waste is shredded into smaller pieces or flakes. These flakes are then cleaned to remove contaminants such as labels, dirt, and residues. Extrusion is a key process in the mechanical recycling of plastic waste. The cleaned plastic flakes are fed into a screw extruder, a machine equipped with a long, heated barrel. As the plastic moves along the screw, it is gradually heated to its melting point. The melted plastic is then extruded through a die into the shape or form wanted, like filaments. The extruded plastic is then cooled, and the cooled solidified plastic is typically cut into granulates. The chemical structure of the plastic is not changed in mechanical recycling.

Mechanical recycling is currently the main recycling process for plastics. In 2020 of all collected post-consumer plastic waste 34,6% was sent to recycling of which only 0,2% was chemically recycled and the rest mechanically (Plastics Europe, 2021). Mechanical recycling is mature technology and widely used for processing single-polymer plastic waste, such as PET, PE, PP, and polystyrene, but also mixed plastic waste streams can be treated mechanically in some cases (Hahladakis, 2020).

Mechanically recycled plastic can replace virgin plastics in the production of the same, similar, or completely different product. Mechanical recycling is categorized into two categories based on the properties of recycled plastic, known as closed-loop and open-loop. Closed-loop recycling or upcycling is more desired of the two. In closed-loop recycling the properties of the recycled plastic remain the similar as the virgin material. Therefore, recycled plastic can be reprocessed into same original products and thus reduce the dependence on the virgin plastics. One of the most successful and widely implemented closed-loop recycling of plastic is turning PET bottles into new PET bottles (Hahladakis, 2020).

On the contrary, open-loop recycling also known as downcycling or cascading the properties of the recycled plastic are downgraded to lower quality making it not suitable for production of same products. Plastic can undergo mechanical treatment only few times before it loses its too much of its quality for closed-loop applications. However, it can be used to produce other products that do not require as high-quality plastic. Being less desirable of the two, it is still the inevitable fate of the plastics in mechanical recycling and a viable solution for material recovering. The material from PET bottles that has undergone mechanical recycling a few times and thus degraded, can be still reprocessed for example to street furniture or plastic lumber (Hahladakis, 2020).

2.4.2 Chemical recycling

While mechanical recycling is a more established technology, chemical recycling is a relatively novel and promising technology which is classified into four main technologies: dissolution, depolymerisation, pyrolysis, and gasification. These technologies have different principles but all of them can convert plastic waste into monomers or smaller hydrocarbon molecules which can be refined into virgin plastics or added value products. However, they all differ by for example, feedstock tolerances to impurities and organic contamination, yields, emissions factors, costs, levels of maturity and types of outputs. The chemical recycling technologies with the highest technological readiness are pyrolysis, catalytic cracking, and conventional gasification. In pyrolysis, the degradation of organic materials takes place under the effect of heat in the absence of oxygen. Depending on the process conditions and type of plastic waste, pyrolysis typically yields a mixture of wax and oil as the main product. The degradation of plastics can also be affected by using a catalyst as heat transfer media. With this process, known as catalytic pyrolysis, more specific reaction pathways can be promoted, leading to higher yields of the desired target products (Qureshi, et al., 2020), (Kaminsky, 2021).

One of the main challenges in chemical recycling of plastic waste is the complexity of its composition. Mixed plastic streams from municipal sectors typically contain mixtures of polyethylene, polypropylene, polystyrene, PET, and multilayer packaging. Multilayer packaging consists of a variety of different polymers and other materials, laminated, or extruded together to form a single packaging unit. Common materials used for layers alongside PE or PP include PET (as a barrier against moisture and chemicals), aluminium (as a barrier also against light and UV), EVOH (as an oxygen barrier) and nylon (polyamide, for strength and barrier properties) (Genuino, Ruiz, Heeres, & Kersten, 2022).

The main challenge with the mixture of different plastics is their reactivity and product distribution during pyrolysis. Polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) are the most common plastics in packaging and also the most desired feedstock for pyrolysis. The absence of any functional groups or heteroatoms in the polymeric structure make them ideal for the production of petrochemical intermediates. The optimal temperature for high liquid yield is close to 550 °C, while higher temperature results in more gaseous product formation. The product from thermal pyrolysis of PE and PP contains typically paraffinic compounds with a wide hydrocarbon distribution (liquid and waxes). The presence of tertiary carbon in the PP structure affects the reactivity, which results in a lighter product compared to PE. Secondary upgrading of the pyrolysis oil from PP and PE might still be needed to produce suitable compounds for the petrochemical industry. A longer residence time during pyrolysis can also increase the liquid yield, but the composition can change from mainly paraffinic hydrocarbons to more aromatic hydrocarbons (Anuar Sharuddin, Abnisa, Wan Daud, & Aroua, 2016), (Soni, et al., 2021).

2.5 Feedstock specifications

Many feedstock specifications for mechanical recycling have been developed and these specifications have defined the plastic waste collection and sorting practices to feed mechanical recyclers. These specifications are, however, insufficient for the chemical recycler using pyrolysis.

A model feedstock specification has been developed using information shared by several operators regarding their feedstock requirements. The input feedstock may require additional sorting and purification steps, which in return influences the cost effectiveness of the process. It is also important to note that many pyrolysis operators are in the early stages of maturation and feedstock specifications may evolve as processes as the technology has been more developed. As described above, pyrolysis is a relatively simple and flexible technology, which usually targets difficult-to-recycle polyolefins, which can include multi material packaging. Other materials are usually held as contaminants because they cause undesirable effects including lowering process yield, reduced output quality and wear on the equipment. Tolerance of the contaminant varies according to the type of contaminant, the operator's specific process operating parameters, output purification process and the quality requirements of the offtaker.

The quality specifications for feedstocks for pyrolysis are:

- Minimum 85 % PE or PP
- Maximum moisture 7 %
- Maximum total contamination 15 %
- Maximum amount of PVC/PVDC 1 %, some operators have a near-zero tolerance
- Maximum amount of PET/EVOH/Nylon 5 %
- Maximum amount of rigid metal/glass/dirt/fines 7 %
- Maximum amount of paper/organics 10 %

2.5.1 Polyolefins

Rigid polyolefins have a valuable offtake market by mechanical recyclers, while the presence of non-targeted polymer grades, colours, odours, and the use of varying additives remain challenging. Pyrolysis operators could target the remainder, but volumes are likely to be low. Many pyrolysis operators are therefore targeting flexible polyolefins. Especially flexible film plastic packaging, in particular from household waste, is not generally collected for mechanical recycling and therefore they have a great potential for the chemical recycling. Mechanical recycling of PE films is mostly limited to post-industrial and high-quality post-consumer material and predominately in larger uncoloured formats.

While PP is a highly recyclable material, post-consumer PP film is rarely separated into a distinct stream. In Europe, it is usually grouped into a mixed plastics or mixed polyolefin output or sorted as a contaminant into a reject stream destined for energy recovery or landfill. The reason behind this is that recycling of PP film is challenging, because it is often found in small formats with high levels of ink e.g., snack food wrappers.

2.5.2 Polyvinyl chloride

PVC is the third most produced polymer and extensively used in the manufacturing of pipes for municipal and industrial applications due to its mechanical strength and chemical resistivity to acids, bases, fats, and some solvents. The presence of chlorine in the molecule results in excellent fire-resistant properties. Therefore, PVC is used for cable insulation and in electrical equipment. Before PVC can be made into finished products, it always requires conversion into a compound by the incorporation of additives. For instance, the heat stability of raw PVC is poor, which is improved by the use of heat stabilizers during polymer processing. Contrary to its multipurpose applications, PVC is not suitable for pyrolysis due to the release of corrosive HCl and other toxic chlorinated hydrocarbons (Anuar Sharuddin, Abnisa, Wan Daud, & Aroua, 2016), (Soni, et al., 2021).

2.5.3 Polystyrene

PS is hard, brittle, and generally transparent. Due to the glass transition temperature above 100 °C, PS can be exploited to make foams (EPS produced by moulding process or Styrofoam by extrusion process). Styrofoam is widely used as building insulation materials including concrete forms and panel systems. Furthermore, PS is inexpensive, durable, and light and therefore widely used in protective packaging, containers lids, bottles and more. Chemical recycling of polystyrene via pyrolysis is of great industrial interest with styrene being the primary product of interest. Very high liquid yields (> 97 wt%) has been reported for the pyrolysis of PS. Styrene has been the main product detected from the liquid followed by benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (Zayoud, et al., 2022), (Anuar Sharuddin, Abnisa, Wan Daud, & Aroua, 2016).

2.5.4 Polyethylene terephthalate

PET is the fourth most produced polymer used in synthetic fibres, beverage bottles, containers of food material and electronics. Although PET is used in many applications, as of 2022 only bottles are collected at a substantial scale and mostly recycled back into bottles by closed-loop mechanical recycling. The rest goes into fibres, film, thermoformed packaging and strapping (NATURAL MINERAL WATERS EUROPE, 2024).

Since PET has oxygen in its structure it is not desired for pyrolysis. Pyrolysis of PET results in a high yield of gas fraction, a low amount of liquids, a significant yield of solid fraction, and a solid residue that remained in the reactor coating sand particles. The main products obtained are carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, benzoic acid, and acetaldehyde (Artetxe, et al., 2010).

2.5.5 Mixed plastic waste

Multi-material films can consist of a variety of different polymers and other materials and are therefore not suitable for mechanical recycling. One example of the composition of a multi-material multi-layer film is a PET/ PE laminate at a ratio of 12 to 58, which means 17% of the structure is PET. The PET content of a bale of this composition would likely be too high for a pyrolysis operator. Mixing of this bale with one that have a higher percentage of PE or PP would then be needed before it can be fed into the pyrolysis (Gendell & Lahme, 2022).

Another important aspect in the area of mixed plastic waste pyrolysis is the presence of contaminants and additives in the feed. For example, organic and paper and cardboard derived contaminants may be present in real plastic wastes, which arise from labels, caps, lids, food residues, etc., introducing unwanted elements in the feeds. Additives are commonly added to polymers to enhance their properties and lifespan. Typical additives are plasticizers, antioxidants, antistatic agents, UV blockers, pigments, and flame retardants. The most common unwanted elements in these contaminants and additives are different metals (Ca, Al, Na, Zn, and Fe) and halogens (Cl, F). These heteroatoms may cause some corrosion of reactors caused by halogens and sulphur, deposition and coking in the reactor due

to the presence of metals, and deactivation of catalyst in further refining of the pyrolysis oil (Genuino, Ruiz, Heeres, & Kersten, 2022). There are therefore some limitations for the plastic grades and amount of contaminants which can be accepted for pyrolysis.

2.6 Measures to increase circularity of plastics

2.6.1 Design for recycling and Eco-design

Incorporating lifecycle and circular thinking into product design (i.e., design for recycling) can significantly reduce future waste, pollution, and toxins. One example of problematic product design is multi-layer materials, such as high-performance food packaging, which are composed of multiple complex layers of different plastics. These multilayer structures often consist mainly of polyethylene (PE) due to its low cost, with additional layers of other plastics like polyethylene terephthalate (PET) for toughness and ethylene-vinyl alcohol (EVOH) for oxygen barrier properties. The separation and recycling of these layers are often difficult or impossible (Ragaert, 2017).

Multilayer packaging poses a specific problem for recyclability. It combines different polymeric and other materials such as paper or aluminium to create customized property profiles with low material consumption. Multilayers can reduce costs by replacing expensive polymers with less costly ones, reducing film thickness, or using recycled materials. According to Schmidt et al. (2022), approximately 17% to 20% of plastic packaging consists of multilayer packaging. Major brands recognize the need to shift towards higher recyclability (Schmidt, Grau, Auer, Maletz, & Jörg, 2022). Many of the largest producers are transitioning from plastic to bio-based packaging and/or to monolayer (or nearly monolayer) materials that can be more easily recycled within existing streams. Packaging World has highlighted monolayer materials such as microwavable monolayer PP pouches for rice dishes (Amcor, JM Packaging) and Unilever Japan's personal care pouch by Toppan, which fits the PET stream thanks to its thin, vapor-deposited barrier layer (Reynolds, 2021).

Eco-design is primarily applied to plastic packaging, aiming to minimize the environmental impacts of plastic packaging and packed goods over their entire life cycle. The eco-design of packaging, which currently constitutes a significant part of municipal solid waste, is addressed in the proposed revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWD) (Nov. 2022). This revision requires all plastic packaging placed on the EU market to contain a minimum amount of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste by January 2030. Additionally, the EU's Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (2018) stipulates that all plastic packaging placed on the EU market should be either reusable or recyclable in a cost-effective manner by 2030. The new proposal for a Regulation on Eco-design requirements, published on March 30, 2022, aims to reduce the life cycle environmental impacts of products sold in the EU. The expected Eco-design Regulation will establish new requirements based on sustainability and circularity parameters. It emphasizes factors such as durability, reusability, upgradability and reparability, recycled content of products, and products' carbon and environmental footprints, among others.

2.6.2 Extended Producer Responsibility

Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) is an environmental policy that holds producers accountable for the end-of-life management of their products (Kosior & Mitchell, Current industry position on plastic production and recycling, 2020). EPR shifts the cost of waste management from local governments to the industry that produces the goods, thereby incentivizing the creation of more easily recyclable products. This policy encourages industries to take back their end-of-life products, prompting them to design products that are more recyclable or reusable. Consequently, this minimizes production costs for the industry by allowing the reuse of recovered materials in new products (Kosior & Crescenzi, Solutions to the plastic waste problem on land and in the oceans, 2020).

A successful example of the EPR scheme is the Deposit Return System (DRS) for PET bottles. This system operates by assigning a monetary value to each bottle, which the customer pays upon purchasing a beverage. This money is then refunded to the customer when the empty bottle is returned to a local retailer. The success of the DRS in PET bottle collection may prompt wider adoption across Europe, improving collection quality and reducing contamination caused by separately collected bottle streams (Eunomia, 2022). An expansion of the DRS to plastic products other than PET bottles could lead also there to fewer material losses due to higher collection rates and lastly to higher quality recyclates.

2.6.3 Circular business models

Circular business models (CBMs) in the circular plastics economy have predominantly focused on recycling, a common strategy that does not necessitate a shift in the core business model. Recycling targets and the use of recyclates are driven by national and EU-level legislation. Recently, new business models with circularity at their core have been emerging. These include designing out unnecessary plastic-based products like packaging, reusing plastic packaging, and repairing equipment by replacing broken plastic components.

Use-cases often involve creating value from waste and substituting fossil-based polymers with bioplastics (Dijkstra, 2020). Efforts to use recycled plastics in high-value products are also being pursued. For example, the EU PRIMUS project includes demonstrations in the automotive and electrical equipment sectors. Additionally, Electrolux and recycler Coolrec have collaborated to create a refrigerator made from recyclate, which won first place in the Automotive, Electrical & Electronic Product category at the Plastics Recycling Awards Europe 2023.

Sustainable actions aimed at achieving higher circularity have been driven by various external and internal factors, including regulatory or industry pressure, organizational commitment, and competition and collaboration. The main opportunities for circular plastics include gaining a competitive advantage and improving resource use efficiency. However, significant barriers have been reported, such as the

high investment and transition costs associated with new innovations, particularly new technologies or system shifts like implementing take-back systems. Additionally, new methods of delivering products or services may necessitate changes in customer behaviour or relationships, both in B2B and B2C contexts.

2.7 Gaps in current circularity of plastics

There are still many challenges to overcome in the transition towards a circular economy of plastics. The challenges can be divided into technological, economical, operational, and regulatory barriers (Siltaloppi, 2021). Technological and operational barriers relate for instance to insufficient collection and recycling processes that limit the valorisation of plastic waste streams. Furthermore, the complicated and expensive process for recycling plastic leads to a higher price compared to virgin plastic, making it often also an economical barrier. Thus, advancements in technology and operational development are needed to overcome these barriers (Siltaloppi, 2021).

Increasing both the collection and recycling rates of plastic waste will be needed to enhance the circularity of plastics. However, current plastic collection schemes vary across Europe and even within the Nordic region. While post-consumer plastic packaging waste is generally well-collected in this area, most of it is still incinerated for energy recovery rather than being recycled (Plastics Europe, 2022). This is because this waste stream is complex, containing mixed plastics such as multi-layer materials, flexible films, and black plastics, which are difficult to sort and recycle mechanically. Consequently, a significant portion is rejected. In TREASoURcE, we focus on these rejected fractions to evaluate their suitability for chemical recycling through pyrolysis. This process produces hydrocarbon molecules that can be refined into virgin plastics or value-added products, thus extracting more value from the waste stream compared to incineration.

Agricultural and municipal rigid plastics from households are often collected as mixed waste, which is rarely sorted, resulting in only a tiny fraction being mechanically recycled. To better understand the composition of these waste streams and evaluate their potential for recycling and increased circularity, in TREASoURcE we collected samples from waste handlers and conducted a "rigid plastic campaign" in the Tampere region, which will be presented in this report.

Chemical recycling, such as pyrolysis, will have a significant impact on the circular economy of plastics and will be needed as complementary technology alongside mechanical recycling to reach the ambitious recycling targets set by the EU Commission. However, research has been going on for the last decades to implement this technology in the commercial stage. Many technological challenges that chemical recycling faces are related to factors prior recycling such as variations in feedstock quality and composition, which are also part of the investigations in TREASoURcE. But also, regulatory barriers are hampering its implementation. Under current EU legislation chemical recycling does not count towards recycling targets. There are individual pieces of legislation in individual countries in Europe

TREASoURcE

that do accept chemical recycling but the regulatory approach across Europe remains inconsistent and uncertain, which consequently holds back investments in this technology (Victory, 2023).

3 TREASoURcE circular plastics demonstrations and their results

3.1 Selection of waste streams

TREASoURcE is focusing on plastic waste streams that are not currently being recycled at all or are otherwise underutilised. Four feedstocks (industrial and municipal) from various providers gave a selection of plastic fractions to exemplify and optimise new regional plastic recycling value chains. These included:

- 1) Unsorted municipal household plastic waste (mostly packaging, rigid, and flexible) from Fredrikstad, Norway, and from Finland (provided by Fortum) as well as unsorted rejected waste (remaining fraction after automated sorting) also provided by Fortum in Finland;
- 2) Industrial plastic waste (technical hard plastic engineering plastics) provided by Vipak in Finland;
- 3) Agricultural post-consumer mixed and sorted plastic waste streams from Finland (provided by MTK);
- 4) Plastic foil from shredded EV batteries (Norway);

Altogether, 10 different feedstocks have been evaluated:

Table 1. Feedstocks analysed and evaluated in TREASoURcE project.

Country of Origin	Company/region	Plastics key waste stream	PCR/PIR	Content of waste	Suitability for mechanical/chemical recycling
Norway	Fredrikstad	Municipal	PCR	Mixed (Polyolefin-rich)	●, ■
Finland	Tampere/Pirkanmaa	Municipal	PCR	Mixed, manually collected, sorted & pretreated (Polyolefin-rich)	●, ■
Finland	Fortum	Municipal	PCR	Mixed reject after sorting (Polyolefin-rich)	■
Finland	Fortum	Municipal	PCR	Mixed (Polyolefin-rich)	■
Finland	Vipak	Industrial	PIR	Mixed (Polyolefin-rich)	■
Finland	Clean Plastic	Agricultural	PCR	Sorted high quality grade (LLDPE)	●, ■
Finland	Clean Plastic	Agricultural	PCR	Mixed reject after sorting (Grade-1) (Polyolefin-rich)	■
Finland	Clean Plastic	Agricultural	PCR	Mixed reject after sorting (Grade-2) (Polyolefin-rich)	■
Finland	Individual farm	Agricultural	PCR	Manually collected, sorted and pretreated (PE mixture)	●, ■

Norway	Fredrikstad	Industrial	PCR	Shredded EV battery foil (PE) and carbon black	Not suitable
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●: Suitable for mechanical recycling

■: Suitable for chemical recycling

PCR: Post-consumer recyclate

PIR: Post-industrial recyclate

3.1.1 Municipal household plastic waste (Norway and Finland)

Household or post-consumer plastic waste in municipalities is primarily composed of everyday items like plastic bottles and packaging. This waste category can encompass a variety of plastics, with PE, PP, and PET being the most common. It is important to note that the post-consumer plastic waste stream often includes foreign materials and contaminants. These can range from additives and paper to glass and even hazardous substances, which can be introduced due to inadequate sorting by consumers or businesses. As a result, despite often being collected separately, the post-consumer plastic waste stream is highly heterogeneous (Lange, 2021).

3.1.2 Agricultural plastic waste (Finland)

At the beginning of the project, MTK identified efficient methods for collecting agricultural plastic materials for their experiments. It quickly became apparent that the acquired test batches were quite small. As a result, it was concluded that it would not be practical to gather samples from multiple farms. Because a significant amount of material would have had to be manually processed and there was uncertainty about where additional material could be sourced for further processing.

In Finland, the further processing of agricultural plastic waste is currently handled mostly by Clean Plastic Finland Oy. To ensure the reliability of the tests, MTK decided to request sample batches from Clean Plastic Finland. In addition to these samples, MTK also included plastics from a single farm as a control material in their tests. This approach ensured a comprehensive and reliable testing process.

3.1.3 Municipal rigid plastics from households (Finland)

Currently, Finland does not have a nationwide recycling program for municipal rigid plastic. However, there are some local collection points and recycling processes in place. For instance, in the capital area, rigid plastics are collected at Sortti collection stations, as reported by the Helsinki Region Environmental Services in 2024 (Helsinki Region Environmental Services, 2024).

Figure 5: Example of municipal rigid plastic.

In Pirkanmaa, also known as Tampere region, a long-term pilot has been conducted in the municipality of Orivesi. Here, residents can bring rigid and packaging plastics to the Orivesi waste station free of charge (Orivesi municipality, 2024).

Despite the existence of these local recycling processes, the recycling rates for rigid plastics remain relatively low. According to the analyses of the Closed Plastic Circle project, only 1% of rigid plastics were recycled in the capital area in 2022 (Sahimaa;Saario;Järvinen;Pitkämäki;& Kangastie, 2023).

Generally, all household plastic waste, apart from packaging plastics, is collected as mixed waste. In 2023, approximately 3% of the collected mixed waste consisted of plastics. It is important to note that this figure does not include packaging plastics (Suomen Kiertovoima, 2024) In 2022, Finland collected around 1,455,875 tons of mixed waste (Statistics Finland, 2024). This implies that annually, approximately 43,676.25 tons of non-packaging plastics are collected through mixed waste.

Given these figures, it is clear that there is significant room for improvement in increasing the recycling rate of rigid plastics in Finland. As a result, rigid plastics have been chosen as one of the primary materials for recycling efforts.

Rigid plastic waste from households comprises various types of plastics, including PP, HDPE, and PVC. For effective recycling, this waste must be sorted. From a process perspective, there are several options: using separate collection containers for each type of plastic or employing manual or automated sorting facilities. However, due to the large size of many rigid plastic items, using separate containers for each type would require substantial space and additional logistics. Furthermore, the likelihood of sorting errors made by individuals is high.

Experiences from a "rigid plastic campaign" conducted by EKOF in the Tampere region suggest that automatic sorting facilities for rigid plastic are rare. Manual sorting is prevalent in many locations, and even some global companies lack automated sorting lines. This could be attributed to the relatively small volumes of rigid plastic waste, at least in Finland, which deter investment and increase process costs. Therefore, there is a need for new technologies that can efficiently identify plastic items.

3.1.4 Plastic from shredded EV batteries (Norway)

Batteries of electric vehicles (EV) are constructed from a variety of polymers with different mechanical, insulation, fire-resistant, and chemical resistant properties. The most common polymers found in EV batteries are polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), polyvinylchloride (PVC), acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polycarbonate (PC), polyurethane (PU), polyamide (PA), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyethylene naphthalate (PEN), and epoxy resins (Richfields, 2024). These polymers have very different chemical compositions and properties and therefore, the separation of the individual polymers from each other is needed before their recycling either mechanically or chemically. In addition, these polymers are often contaminated with metals and carbon black from the electrodes or fluorine from the electrolyte, which makes them unsuitable for both mechanical and chemical recycling.

3.2 Pre-treatment and recycling technologies in TREASoURcE

3.2.1 MODIX Modular mixer

Conventional extrusion processes of bulky plastic waste require multiple steps before extrusion, such as shredding and pelletizing, due to the limitations of feeding large plastic parts directly into the feeding zone. MODIX is a novel extruder developed by VTT equipped with two nested cylinders where the molten plastic passes through, enabling a large contact area for accurate temperature control together with high shear. Plastic feedstocks which are cleaned from non-melting contaminations such as metals, soil, electrical & electronical components (e.g., microelectronics, batteries, etc.) are preferred in this process. One of the most important benefits of MODIX is its large feeding zone which allows feeding bulky, heterogenous material directly without the need for shredding or granulation. The size of the feeding materials is reduced to the size of the feeder to facilitate a smooth feeding process. It is possible to feed a variety of material forms such as shredded plastic pieces, foams, bulky sheets, films, and textiles. Hence, the MODIX processing has less pre-treatment requirements for the input plastic waste material compared to conventional mechanical recycling and produces a compacted homogenous material (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Traditional extrusion vs. Modular mixer (MODIX) developed by VTT.

The output material of MODIX can be used in further mechanical recycling or compounding processes to formulate thermoplastic resin compounds. MODIX can also be utilized as a pretreatment step for pyrolysis thanks to its compacting and homogenization ability of the mixed plastic waste where the output can directly be fed into a pyrolysis reactor. MODIX not only ensures efficient mixing with relatively short screw length, but also enables the possibility for long processing times to improve homogenization. Another purpose is the removal of volatiles and potentially hazardous gases from the waste feedstock. Application areas of MODIX ranges from textiles to packaging, automotive, home appliances, bioplastics, and a variety of other uses.

3.2.2 Advanced mechanical recycling: VAREX

Figure 7: VAREX tandem extrusion line for advanced extrusion/mechanical recycling.

VAREX is a tandem extrusion line with adaptive in-line melt rheology control for advanced mechanical recycling (Figure 7). Stabilizing and upgrading the material properties of recycled plastics (i.e., value retention or even increase) are achieved by (1) Melting and filtering of the recycled material. (2) Smart dosing of additives (e.g., virgin polymer, stabilizers, compatibilizers, chain extenders etc.) which assists fine-tuning of the compound formulation during extrusion. (3) Upgrading and homogenization of the material properties (e.g., viscosity, thermal/mechanical properties, compatibilization etc.) to ideally virgin-like levels.

VAREX equipment's in-line melt rheology monitoring and control system enables detecting the fluctuations of especially rheological properties and helps homogenization of polymeric compounds.

3.3 Collection, pre-treatment, and analyses of TREASoURcE feedstocks

3.3.1 Collection of agricultural plastics

Through various investigations and discussions with organizations such as Clean Plastic Finland Oy, the Älymuovi project (maatalousmuovijate.fi, 2024), and the MuKi project (Hytönen, 2024), it has been determined that the cleanliness and storage conditions of plastic are of major importance, particularly

in the context of agricultural plastics. When properly processed and stored, such material serves as an excellent raw material for recycled plastics.

The method of plastic collection is a crucial factor. For instance, plastic films and gauzes should not be wrapped around boards or other materials. Instead, each package should contain only one type of plastic to ensure the quality of the recycled product. It is also important to remove large stones and trash from the plastics. This step prevents damage to the recycling plant's equipment and ensures a smoother recycling process. Additionally, excess ink and adhesives can hinder the recycling process and should be removed as much as possible. Different types of plastics, as well as different colours, should be sorted separately. For example, packing plastic bales in a bag made of a different type of plastic can slow down and complicate the recycling process. Lastly, plastics should be stored in a dry environment and protected from light, especially during long-term storage. This precaution helps to preserve the quality of the plastic and ensures it remains suitable for recycling.

Examples of effective practices already implemented have been compiled, and information about these practices has been disseminated through various communication channels. These practices provide insights into how farmers can store collected plastics more efficiently. For instance, MTK presented some innovative 'homemade' solutions in their Christmas calendar. One such solution involves the recycling of plastics from feed bales. To streamline the collection and storage process, the farm uses a 'self-tied' bale press. This device compresses the plastics from several tens of bales into compact bundles. These bundles can then be conveniently moved or stored as needed¹. These practices highlight the potential for creative, on-site solutions to enhance the efficiency of plastic recycling processes in agricultural settings. By adopting such practices, farmers can contribute to more sustainable and effective recycling efforts.

3.3.2 Analysis of agricultural plastic waste

Clean Plastic Finland is recycling the main part of the agricultural plastic in Finland. Before the delivery of the plastic to the company, farmers have separated the white plastics from the coloured ones (Figure 8). In addition to this, farmers must ensure that the plastic is clean and does not contain any soil or other contaminants.

Clean Plastic Finland's production unit located in Merikarvia consist of a versatile pre-treatment and washing line to mechanically recycle the agricultural plastic. From the production unit, three different sample fractions were delivered to VTT for further analyses and processing:

Figure 8: Sorted and unsorted agricultural plastic waste to be delivered to Clean Plastic Finland.

¹ Link to a video about the processes, posted on LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7141678130540314624>.

- Recycled agricultural plastic
- Reject 1, dirty
- Reject 2, clean

Figure 9: Recycled agricultural plastic and rejects delivered by Clean Plastic Finland.

The plastic waste fractions were analysed to assess their polymer composition (by DSC) (Figure 10), elemental composition, heating value, and metals (Table 2 and Table 3). Before the analyses, rejects from Clean Plastic Finland were treated by MODIX to homogenize the samples (Figure 6). Since the agricultural plastic was consisting mostly of PE grades, rejects were fed to MODIX without any prior washing and drying steps. The outputs were collected as extrudates (visible in the upper part of Figure 11) and further shredded into smaller pieces before the analyses.

The DSC results (Figure 10) indicate that the reject samples consisted mainly of LDPE and HDPE. In comparison, municipal plastic waste from Fredrikstad contained also PP and polyester (most likely PET).

Figure 10. Differential thermograms of the analysed agricultural and municipal plastic waste.

Figure 11: Agricultural plastic waste rejects before and after MODIX pretreatment.

Table 2. Elemental composition and heating value of the analysed agricultural plastics.

	Unit	Recycled agricultural plastic	Reject 1	Reject 2
Heating value				
HHV	MJ/kg	44.99	35.52	39.81
LHV	MJ/kg	41.05	32.96	37.43
Elemental composition				
Carbon	wt%	82.7	65.9	74.6
Hydrogen	wt%	12.2	11.7	10.9
Nitrogen	wt%	0.1	0.3	0.2

The metal content of the agricultural plastics samples was determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma Spectroscopy (ICP) and the results are shown in Table 3. In all three samples, Ti was found to be the most dominant inorganic element, reaching up to ~1.8% (by weight). This result is not surprising, as titanium oxide is commonly used as white pigment in plastics. Other elements with a relatively high amount are Ca, Mg, Na, K, Fe, Al, and Si, which are most likely ingredients of commonly used fillers, pigments, and coatings, or residues from the substances that have previously been stored in these plastics. It is also worth to mention that hazardous elements, such as As, Cd, Cr, Hg, and Pb were only found in traces well below legal limits (ROHSGuide.com, 2024).

Table 3. Metal content (ICP) of the analysed agricultural plastics.

Element	Unit	Recycled agricultural plastic	Reject 1	Reject 2
As	mg/kg	0.38	-	-
Ba	mg/kg	1.4	-	-
Cd	mg/kg	<0.04	-	-
Co	mg/kg	0.1	-	-
Cr	mg/kg	130	350	300
Cu	mg/kg	20	120	29
Hg	mg/kg	<0.08	-	-
Mn	mg/kg	2.5	140	25
Mo	mg/kg	<0.4	-	-
Ni	mg/kg	2	7.2	3.8
Pb	mg/kg	2.8	23	4.6
Se	mg/kg	<1	-	-
Sb	mg/kg	5.2	-	-
Sn	mg/kg	0.72	-	-
Sr	mg/kg	<1	41	15
Tl	mg/kg	<0.1	-	-
V	mg/kg	0.33	3.6	<1
Zn	mg/kg	23	61	34
Ca	mg/kg	200	3600	1600
Mg	mg/kg	21	940	330
Na	mg/kg	63	2600	1300
K	mg/kg	<100	2500	870
P	mg/kg	64	320	170
S	mg/kg	100	330	250

Fe	mg/kg	400	3600	1400
Al	mg/kg	650	6400	3100
Si	mg/kg	<400	16000	4000
Ti	mg/kg	18000	11000	13000
Ba	mg/kg	1.4	110	29
Cl	mg/kg	250	-	-
Br	mg/kg	<10	-	-

Mechanically recycled LLDPE polymer provided by Clean Plastic Finland was processed with the VAREX advanced extrusion line (Advanced mechanical recycling) which provides in-line monitoring of rheological properties. In Table 4, the improvement in ultimate tensile strength, Young's Modulus and Stress at Break are attributed to homogenization of linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE) plastic waste feedstock under extrusion.

Table 4. Comparison of mechanical properties of LLDPE provided by Clean Plastic Finland before and after the VAREX advanced extrusion process.

Material properties	LLDPE	
	before VAREX process	after VAREX process
Ultimate tensile strength (Mpa)	13.8	15.8
Young's Modulus (Mpa)	136	146
Stress at Break (Mpa)	13.8	15.8
Strain at Break (%)	5.5	4.9

Figure 12: Viscosity measurements of LLDPE agricultural plastic waste material by 3 different methods.

LLDPE was processed with the VAREX equipment by VTT to observe the rheological behaviour. Consistency and viscosity data of the material was collected during extrusion at 170°C. Viscosity and MFI measurements were collected also by an offline rheometer at 190°C. MFI data were transformed into apparent viscosity data. Offline rheometer and MFI measurements show that the viscosity of LLDPE did not change significantly after VAREX processing. In-line rheometer data collected during VAREX extrusion is comparable with the offline viscosity data (Figure 12).

3.3.3 Rigid plastic waste

Rigid plastic waste collected by EKOF in the Tampere region was analysed by VTT with Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF).

The differential thermograms of the 2nd heating cycle of the DSC analysis of the 4 sorted fractions are shown in Figure 13. It is evident that the PP-based fractions 1, 2, and 3 include almost only PP polymer types as there was only a single melting peak observed between 162-168°C, except for PP fraction 1, which also has a separate minor melting peak at 120°C, attributed to PE. It is common that PP fractions contain a certain amount of PE, as both materials can be blended or copolymerized intentionally to achieve certain material properties or because the general handling of the waste and existing sorting technologies do not yield pure PP. For the HDPE fraction the only melting peak observed was at 133.5°C, which is characteristic for HDPE.

Figure 13: Differential thermograms of the 2nd heating cycle of three different PP fractions and one HDPE fraction.

The FTIR results of all characterised fractions that were sorted during the rigid plastic waste collection campaign are in line with the DSC results and showed no other polymers than PP and HDPE to be present. That means, the collected plastic waste stream contains only polyolefins and thus offers a remarkable potential for both mechanical and chemical recycling technologies.

Table 5. XRF elemental analysis results of four different fractions obtained and sorted in the rigid plastics collection campaign.

Element	PP Fraction-1 (ppm)	PP Fraction-2 (ppm)	PP Fraction-3 (ppm)	HDPE Fraction (ppm)
Al	5378	2941	1849	4252
Si	4103	30070	3101	2674
P	179	ND	ND	152
S	ND	1243	222	ND
Cl	679	ND	ND	ND
K	ND	ND	ND	ND
Ca	1448	2178	13698	170
Ti	6139	11034	19178	650
Cr	ND	468	ND	ND
Fe	357	4412	184	114
Co	ND	53	ND	ND
Ni	ND	545	ND	ND
Cu	111	70	ND	ND
Zn	ND	144	ND	ND

Sb	69	ND	ND	ND
Ba	ND	ND	ND	245
Nd	174	214	279	239
Th	262	ND	226	ND

ND: Not detected in significant amounts in quantitative analysis

XRF analysis results of 4 different waste fractions are shown in Table 5. In all 3 PP fractions, Al, Si, Ca, and Ti were found to be the most prevalent inorganic elements, reaching up to ~5% (by weight) in total for PP Fraction 2. This result is not surprising, as these elements are ingredients of commonly used fillers, pigments, and coatings. It is also worth to mention that elements such as Fe, Nd, and Th were found in traces. This could be explained by a possible contamination caused by improper discarding of electronic components confused with household rigid plastic waste or due to cross-contamination, which can be caused by shredding different kinds of plastic waste with the same equipment. In the HDPE fraction, only Al and Si were found at a total level of ~7000 ppm (0.7% by weight), which can be tolerated in the pyrolysis process. After the initial characterisation, the waste fractions were washed, dried, shredded, and subsequently processed in the VAREX line to collect rheological data and as preparation for chemical recycling trails using pyrolysis.

3.3.4 Municipal plastic waste from Fredrikstad, Norway

Mixed plastic household waste collected in Fredrikstad underwent a manual cleaning process, followed by a detailed characterization of its material composition. A significant portion of the items were labelled with a resin identification code (Figure 14), facilitating their categorization. Unlabelled items had their materials identified using FTIR spectroscopy. However, PE identified by FTIR was kept as separate fraction because it was difficult to distinguish whether it is HDPE or LDPE. Items such as laminates and other mixed-material objects were separated. Figure 15 displays a few examples of waste items that were classified as residual and deemed unsuitable for mechanical recycling. The overall composition of the analysed mixed plastic household waste is summarised in Figure 16. Since Norway has a deposit return scheme for PET bottles, there were almost no bottles in the received batch of household waste and most of the PET items were trays.

Figure 14: Resin identification codes.

Figure 15. Waste items that were sorted out as residual during manual sorting. a) Packaging items containing metal parts, b) multi material laminates, and c) items of metal or metal coated plastic films.

Figure 16. Overall composition of the analysed mixed plastic household waste from Fredrikstad, Norway (by weight).

An observation from the material sorting step was that many of the PE and PP waste items analysed by FTIR had an unexpected peak at around 1743 cm^{-1} , which indicates an ester bond. This is most likely related to fat residues from food that have not been completely removed during the cleaning process.

After sorting the plastic waste into fractions of different polymer types, the fractions of HDPE, PP, PS, and PET were shredded to smaller pieces using a blade granulator. Prior further processing, the shredded HDPE, PP, and PS fractions were dried at $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 hours. The PET fraction was dried overnight at $140\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The shredded and dried materials (Figure 17) were subsequently extruded using a mini compounder. Specimens for mechanical testing were prepared by injection moulding (Figure 18). The extrusion temperature was regulated between 200 to $260\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, depending on the polymer type.

Figure 17: Shredded material and injection moulded dumbbells of HDPE (a), PP (b), PS (c), and PET (d).

FTIR analysis of the processed materials indicated that PS and PET were quite pure without traces of other polymers or contaminants. However, the FTIR spectrum of HDPE indicated the presents of a small amount of PP and vice versa the PP sample contained some PE. It is very common that PP is blended with PE either intentionally to improve physical properties or unintentionally due to imperfect sorting during waste handling. The PE content in PP can be estimated by FTIR analysis (Larsen ÅG, 2021) using the peak height (I) ratio of the peaks at 1168 cm⁻¹ and 716 cm⁻¹

%PE is calculated from the ratio $I_{1168} / (I_{1168} + I_{716})$

A calibration curve was prepared beforehand based on analyses of a range of PP/PE blends with known PE content. Whether the PE content in an unknown PP sample is a result of a PP/PE co-polymer or a PP/PE blend cannot be determined from the FTIR analysis. The analysis of the processed PP sample yielded an estimated PE content of about 8 wt%. These results were confirmed by means of Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC).

The results from the tensile testing of the four materials are summarized in Table 6. The values of the recycled materials are within the range of typical values of virgin material of these plastics confirming that they are well suited for manufacturing new products. The four fractions that were processed and analysed constitute about 56 wt% of the received plastic household waste. Hence, with proper sorting and cleaning in place a large proportion of this waste stream could be recycled mechanically.

Table 6. Tensile properties of the recycled materials.

Material	E-Modulus (MPa)	Yield strength (MPa)	Elongation at yield, grip to grip (%)	Stress at break (MPa)	Elongation at break, grip to grip (%)
HDPE	997 ± 9	31.7 ± 0.5	7.2 ± 0.2	6.8 ± 0.7	28 ± 2
PP	1080 ± 23	25.2 ± 0.2	8.9 ± 0.2	5.09 ± 0.05	92 ± 62
PS	2680 ± 44	37.4 ± 0.6	1.79 ± 0.03	29 ± 4	7 ± 5
PET	1790 ± 61	40.6 ± 0.9	3.21 ± 0.03	14 ± 13	7 ± 3

In addition to the manually sorted waste, a small study was conducted at SINTEF using unsorted, washed, and shredded municipal plastic household waste from Fredrikstad, Norway. The study aimed to evaluate the feasibility of this simple sorting method based on density (floating or not floating in water) and the quality of the material after mechanical recycling. The shredded plastic waste was placed in a bucket with 10 litres of tap water, stirred briefly, and then left to settle for approximately 5 hours. Along with plastics, some pieces of wood were observed floating, which eventually sank to the bottom. Both the floating and sinking fractions were manually collected and their compositions were analysed using FTIR spectroscopy.

Figure 18: Injection-moulded specimens from the floating fraction.

The floating fraction, which contained most of the material, was a blend of LDPE, HDPE, and PP with a ratio of 68% PE and 32% PP. The sinking fraction was significantly smaller and contained plastics such as PET, PVC, and PET/PE laminates. Due to the mix of materials in the sinking fraction, it was deemed less suitable for further processing in mechanical recycling.

The floating fraction, consisting only of polyolefins, was selected for a mechanical recycling trial. The material was compounded using an extruder and injection-moulded specimens were prepared for tensile testing (Figure 18). The recycled PE-PP blend was homogeneous with a few impurities and demonstrated acceptable though lower mechanical properties when compared with recycled material from sorted HDPE and PP plastic waste fractions.

This study demonstrated that this simple sorting method of washed and shredded household plastic waste based on density is feasible. The separated PE-PP fraction could be directed towards chemical recycling without necessitating further separation. However, for mechanical recycling further separation of PE and PP is recommended. This is because PE and PP have different melting points and other physical properties and mixing them results in recyclates of lower quality.

3.3.5 Municipal plastic waste from Finland (provided by Fortum)

A sample of the reject from post-consumer plastic waste sorting was delivered to the project by Fortum in Finland. The post-consumer plastic was separately collected and delivered to Fortum's recycling facility, where it was sorted by near-infrared technology. The reject was sampled for the TREASoURcE project had been crushed to particle sizes of around 60 mm and was taken from the process after metal and PVC sorting. The polyolefin content analysed by DSC was in the range of 45-50 wt%. PET content analysed with the same method varied a lot, between 5-20 wt%. Ash content analysed by TGA was between 6-7 wt%.

The sample might contain pathogens and had an undesired odour and because of work safety at VTT, washing of the sample was needed before further processing. In combination with washing, sink-float

sorting was carried out to remove other plastics from polyolefins (Figure 19). The following washing procedures were tested for the Fortum reject:

- 1) Washing in cold water (tap water temperature)
- 2) Washing in hot water (72-75°C)
- 3) Washing in alkali water (NaOH concentration of 2.5%)

Washing was carried out in 20 kg batches in IBC container using 500-700 litres of flotation media (1, 2, or 3). In all strategies, shredding of the feedstock was carried out before washing. Otherwise, some larger plastic objects would not have been cleaned properly and their drying would also have been difficult. A second important thing during washing was to have good friction force between washing brushes/mixing elements and the shredded plastics to really sweep out the adhered dirt onto plastics. The washing took around 10 minutes, but the time for sink-float separation took a bit longer time.

Figure 19. Washing of Fortum reject in an IBC container.

After the washing step, the materials were dried and pretreated with the MODIX equipment (between 250-265°C) to homogenize the material and shredded into smaller sizes (6mm) for further analysis and pyrolysis steps.

The distribution of light (polyolefin rich fraction) and heavy fraction after sink-float separation is presented in Table 7. According to DSC measurements, PET was mainly collected in the heavy fraction. The results were similar for all three different washing procedures. Yield was best in cold water due to the large excess of water.

Table 7. Distribution of light and heavy fractions after sink-float separation [in percent].

	Light fraction	Heavy fraction
Cold water	70	30
Hot water	70	30
Alkali water	65	35

The original reject and the light fractions after warm water and alkali water washing were also analysed for elemental composition, heating value (Table 8), and metal content (Table 9).

Table 8. Elemental composition and heating value of untreated and washed municipal plastic waste reject.

	Unit	Reject from municipal	Light fraction after warm water washing	Light fraction after alkali water washing
Heating value				
HHV	MJ/kg	37.6	39.9	40.7
LHV	MJ/kg	35.2	37.2	38
Elemental composition				
Carbon	wt%	75.9	78.6	79.3
Hydrogen	wt%	11.1	12.4	12.3
Nitrogen	wt%	0.27	0.39	0.49

Table 9. Metal content (ICP) of untreated and washed municipal plastic waste reject.

Element	Unit	Reject from municipal	Light fraction after warm water washing	Light fraction after alkali water washing
As	mg/kg	0.22	<0.2	0.41
Ba	mg/kg	500	500	580
Cd	mg/kg	2.4	2.2	0.7
Co	mg/kg	1.1	0.85	2.6

Cr	mg/kg	31	19	240
Cu	mg/kg	20	24	26
Hg	mg/kg	<0.08	<0.08	<0.08
Mn	mg/kg	15	12	33
Mo	mg/kg	0.96	2.1	6.4
Ni	mg/kg	6.4	7.1	96
Pb	mg/kg	16	41	12
Se	mg/kg	<1	<1	<1
Sb	mg/kg	52	28	37
Sn	mg/kg	12	8.4	2.8
Sr	mg/kg			
Tl	mg/kg	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
V	mg/kg	0.63	0.26	1.6
Zn	mg/kg	89	120	73
Ca	mg/kg	7600	6400	6000
Mg	mg/kg	740	1000	630
Na	mg/kg	920	210	820
K	mg/kg	420	100	<100
P	mg/kg	170	110	100
S	mg/kg	420	260	280
Fe	mg/kg	630	520	1700
Al	mg/kg	3400	2100	1700
Si	mg/kg	2200	2200	2100
Ti	mg/kg	4200	5600	5400
Ba	mg/kg	500	500	580
Cl	mg/kg	4100	2900	2100
Br	mg/kg	<10	20	20

Ca, Al, Si, Ti, and Cl were found to be the most dominant inorganic elements, in the municipal plastic waste reject sample. These elements are ingredients of commonly used fillers, pigments, and coatings, or possibly residues from substances that have previously been stored in these plastics. Interestingly, the washing procedure using warm water vs. alkaline water has little effect on the metal content of the sample. In addition, there is little difference in the elemental composition between the municipal plastic waste reject sample and its light fraction, which contains mostly polyolefins. Further, it is worth to mention that hazardous elements, such as As, Cd, Cr, Hg, and Pb were only found in traces well below legal limits (ROHSGuide.com, 2024).

3.4 Promoting products made from recycled plastics

Procurers are responsible for considerable budgets related to products made from plastic. Uncertainties about cost effects when procuring products related to recycled plastic, uncertainty about available market solutions of products made from recycled plastic and how to verify the recycled contents of recycled plastic in products procured are all issues that can affect the willingness and ability of procurers to demand products made from recycled plastic in their agreements. In the TREASoURcE project the subtask CE-smart procurers led by County of Østfold is reviewing and developing guidance material for procurers to promote both the inclusion of criteria to support the market of products with recycled plastic content as well as the market for reusable plastic solutions. The recipes and guidelines to promote increased circularity of plastics in procurements will be collected and defined in deliverable D2.4, to be delivered January 2026.

3.4.1 Procurement categories for recycled plastic

Guidance material and actions related to promoting the demand for recycled plastic is situated as one of several circular concerns related to CE-smart procurement, where aspects related to reducing consumption, reuse functions, repair services, remanufacturing and other issues in the circular and waste hierarchy also will be addressed. The issue of recycled plastic in public procurements can largely be divided into these main categories:

- Plastic packaging of products bought by municipalities in larger quantities and logistics packaging used for the transportation of the procured products
- *Plastic as a component of products procured*, for instance furniture, IT-equipment, serving trays and medicinal equipment in local healthcare services, waste bags and containers, etc
- **Plastic in construction materials**, like insulation materials, cables, and pipes and in materials of floors and walls and *plastic packaging at construction sites*. Procurements related to construction of buildings are characterized by complex contracts involve designated personnel within public procurement units and are responsible for significant amounts of plastic being sorted for waste incineration. Combined with the high share of climate gas emissions related to construction, this makes it an area with high potential for making a significant impact on circular issues related to plastic and the procurement process.

- **Plastic in textiles:** Among plastic as a component in products textiles make up one of the key areas and value chains, 60% of textiles being made of plastic . Plastic in textiles covers several polymers and fabrics, polyester and nylon being the most widely used. It is estimated that only around 1-2% of fibres are recycled into new clothing (EU strategy for sustainable and circular clothing 2022). Roughly 75% of textiles in the EU are estimated to end up in mixed waste and not being sorted for recycling or reuse (Management of used and waste textiles in Europe's circular economy, European environment agency, 2020). Prioritizing attention to both stakeholder involvement on barriers and opportunities as well as providing relevant guidance material to promote demand for more circular plastic solutions and business models are needed.

3.4.2 Review of existing guidance material

As part of WP2 work we have investigated different procurement materials related to reduction, re-use, and recycling of plastics as well as the different plastic types involved in the products procured. In the process of reviewing existing procurement materials, we have looked at three sources:

- National requirements and criteria to promote reduction of plastic, recycled plastic content and recycling of plastic products procured.
- Checklists on packaging and circular concerns when procuring goods developed in the regional procurement advisory project of Climate Østfold
- Projects on mapping procurements of recycled plastic in goods and procurement handbooks, covering a range of procurement cases resulting in requirements and criteria promoting the use of recycled plastic in procured products.

Plastic as a category and criteria in *national guidance material* leans heavily towards aspects related to pollution and environmental/health risks from specific materials or mainly consider aspects related to standardized requirements for all procurements This is for instance ensuring the products only having packaging necessary to preserve the quality and functions of the products, the labels of the products indicating whether the item in question can be recycled and how it should be sorted. The national procurement tools and criteria of Finland also have included measures and tools for contractors in construction procurements to enable improved sorting of plastic products for recycling.

The review has identified two category-based checklists which comprehensively can be used by procurement advisors to address aspects related to plastic in most public procurements of goods. The checklists are divided into plastic as part of packaging of goods and plastic in procured products as an aspect of circular concerns for procurement of goods. Each checklist follows the waste hierarchy by starting with questions with questions for the higher end of the waste hierarchy and going progressively through the different levels of circularity, suggesting measures to be taken at each level depending on the responses received in the market dialogue. Measures that favour increased circularity, like reduction of packaging or plastic content or reuse/takeback of packaging will be prioritized before recycling. By incorporating the use of the checklists into all public procurement of goods within a municipality or county, circular plastic solutions and demand for products with recycled plastic can be promoted systematically.

The main principles applied to the procurement of packaging or products made from plastic are the following:

1. Packaging or products containing plastic where the plastic or product end up as residual waste should be avoided. This also applies to all kinds of bio-degradable plastic
2. Alternatives to fossil-based plastic should be prioritized, provided they meet durability and functionality requirements and are recyclable.
3. Based on questions in market responses, consider making it a minimum requirement that recycled plastic is used for specific products/specific parts of the packaging/a specific share of the packaging or the product
4. Bio-based plastic should be made from biomass from secondary raw materials

3.4.3 Circular award criteria for recycled plastic

Mapping of a number of case studies of procurements with recycled plastic shows that recycled plastic is developed as minimum requirements and award criteria for both waste containers and waste bags, cleaning products, textiles, school chairs and outdoor furniture. Award criteria for recycled plastic content can be used both as share of post-consumer and pre consumer recycled content or a mixture of the two, post-consumer recycled content share being the most widely used. Combinations of different recycled plastic fibres may affect the quality of the material and also affect the possibility for further recycling. When making award criteria for recycled plastic, procurers should specify the type of plastic fibre that will be awarded for providing recycled content.

The means of verifications used range from environmental product declarations, data sheets, certifications as well as producer declarations, so for some of the relevant markets standardized verification has not yet been developed. Since this market is rapidly evolving questions relating to the means of verification that can be provided should be included in all market dialogue with packaging or products including plastic.

3.4.4 Eco-design of plastic products in guidance material

An identified barrier for both the recyclability of plastic used in the products as well as the recycled content of plastic used in the products is the complicated design of plastic materials and products and the use of composites and multi-layer packaging. Promoting the eco-design of plastic products and packaging through mono-material, single-layer solutions and requirements on design for disassembly into different parts must be included in the procurement procedures and tools to ensure increased demand for products designed for recycling and reuse in the market. To ensure the recyclability of the procured products specifications for the relevant product and plastic type used in the product must be made.

Food packaging, packaging for work clothes, cleaning products, IT-products as well as logistical packaging of all kinds of goods procured constitute areas that should be particularly addressed, since those are goods bought in large quantities by public procurers. To increase the knowledge and capacity of

public procurers to address issues related to eco-design in packaging for these product categories separate seminars will be organized within the TREASoURcE project to show opportunities, case studies and formulas that procurers can use. Findings from these seminars will be integrated into procurement guidance material from the project and the project replication handbook website.

3.4.5 Means of verification of recycled plastic content

The means of verifying the recycled plastic share of a product or packaging is an issue that relates to all procurements, whether the recycled plastic content is used as a minimum requirement or for criterion points. Means of verification for recycled plastic content that are available can vary from product sheets and declarations, certification systems and environmental product declarations. Currently long supplier chains for plastic materials and lack of congruent rules to follow along the supply chain makes it difficult to identify recycled from virgin materials and trace the materials. Standards for recycled plastic are still being developed and existing third-party based certification systems have different standards for calculating recycled content. Some of these, like Recyclclass, are at the time not widely used. (FIPRI, meeting 30.04 and collaboration with Closed Loop project on construction site plastics). This means that procurers will need to trust verification in the form of product sheets or declarations from producers/suppliers and should incorporate contract terms on collaboration with suppliers related to reporting of recycled plastic content and developments related to certification schemes.

The introduction of digital passports for products has the potential to address some of the issues related to lack of secure identification of recycled materials and varying use and standards of certifications for recycled content. In the absence of agreed standards on certifications of recycled content, criterion points for third-party, life-cycle-based labels like the Nordic Svanemerket and EU Ecolabel or being able to provide EPDs for the product can be used to promote the market for increased recycling and circular solutions.

3.4.6 Standardisation of pyrolysis oil

Chemical recycling of plastic waste involves breaking down plastic polymers into their constituent molecules through various chemical processes, such as pyrolysis. These processes allow for the conversion of plastic waste into raw materials or feedstocks that can be used to produce new plastics, fuels, or other valuable products. Pyrolysis is considered as a complementary chemical recycling technology to mechanical recycling of plastics. Pyrolysis oil, derived from the thermal decomposition of plastics, is a promising product for resource recovery. However, the current lacking standardised practices in chemical recycling and recyclate quality control hinders the market penetration for pyrolysis oil.

Pyrolysis oil, classified under UN 3295 – Hydrocarbons liquid, N.O.S., lacks a universal definition due to its diverse origin from various plastic waste feedstocks. Unlike typical commodity products, pyrolysis oil quality and composition depend heavily on the types of plastics used in the pyrolysis process.

The diverse nature of the pyrolysis oil hinders the establishment of standardised classification and quality control measures for pyrolysis oil. In addition, many challenges arise from the varied applications of pyrolysis oils, including plastic production, chemical recycling, steam cracking, petrochemical product refinement, and fuel production. Each application demands specific quality parameters, leading to differing specifications among customers. Consequently, there is no uniform standard for pyrolysis oil, complicating regulatory compliance and certification processes.

To address this issue, companies adhere to individual customer-defined quality and analysis specifications. These specifications often require compliance with regulations such as REACH registration and, increasingly, ISCC+ certification. Polyfuels, TREASoURcE partner, is an industrial operator specializing in the pyrolysis of plastic waste, producing pyrolysis oil. From Polyfuels' operational experience in the field, the following analysis methods and analysis parameters are typical for pyrolysis oil quality used for plastic production (Table 10).

Table 10. Analysis methods and parameters for pyrolysis oil in plastic production

Analysis methods	Typical range for analysis parameters
GC MS and GC FID	Pyrolysis oil contains at least 50 % of Naphta range oils: C8 – C14
Boiling point curve according to ASTM D2887	Preferably lower than 350 °C – ideally around 270 C
Bromine number	Maximum 70 g/100 g

To promote the usage of pyrolysis oil from recycled plastic, standardisation of chemical recycling and pyrolysis oil in addition to further investment in advanced recycling are recommended:

- Establish a stakeholder cooperation platform to develop industry-specific standards and certification schemes for plastic recycling processes and recyclate quality control.
- Create flexible standards that adapt to the dynamic nature of recyclates based on the feedstock composition.
- Periodically review standards to incorporate advancements and market demands as the field of chemical recycling is advancing rapidly.
- Invest in RDI on recycling routes in combinations of mechanical, chemical, and other forms of recycling, with attention to enhanced system design and product quality.

3.5 Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement

The project has initiated collaboration with the Closed Loop project led by municipality of Espoo on methods for and results from market dialogue related to construction site plastic packaging. These networks and actors will be exploited further to validate findings and provide feedback on stakeholder engagement approaches for construction site plastic packaging. Upcoming criteria coming from the Closed Loop project later this year will be evaluated when developing the procurement guidance material from the TREASoURcE project on recycled and circular plastics.

The capacity for sorting and recycling needs to be scaled up in all regions to avoid that sorted plastic waste end up as residual waste or in waste incineration. To include the perspectives of waste handling operators and networks, these actors need to be included in both all capacity building work (seminars and workshops) related to providing guidance for CE-smart procurement and are part of the target groups in many stakeholder actions in the TREASoURcE project, including industry engagement workshops, seminars on CE-smart procurement and specific workshops on circular plastic action for recycling and waste handling networks.

3.5.1 Agricultural plastic waste (Finland)

Discussions about waste management and side streams with stakeholders and farmers in Finland have frequently highlighted agricultural plastics as a significant concern, with a strong desire for rapid improvements. To address this issue, a round table discussion was organized by the Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners (MTK) in May 2023. The objective was to understand what kind of plans Maatalousmuovien kierrätys Oy, a company specializing in the recycling of agricultural plastics, must develop to promote the recycling of agricultural plastics in the coming years. The discussion saw participation from various organizations including MTK, Uusiomuovi, JAMK's eMuovi project, VTT, Ekokumppanit (EKOF), and Business Tampere. The primary focus of these discussions was the development of a new collection system. This system aims to provide farmers with a user-friendly solution, featuring straightforward logistics.

Plastic waste can be collected during designated 'pop-up' collection events or directly from the farms. Farmers have the option to report their recyclable waste for pickup. They can also choose to collaborate with neighbouring farms to streamline the process. While current improvements are geared towards new plastic streams, it is important to note that older agricultural plastics may not be included in these initiatives.

The collaboration with the MuKi and eMuovi projects has proven to be highly beneficial, leading to the exchange of valuable information. One of the key conclusions drawn from these discussions is that more efficient recycling of plastics could significantly enhance the responsibility and public perception of the agricultural sector. To maximize the recycling of agricultural plastics, concerted efforts must be made in the processing of these materials. This includes a particular emphasis on sorting at the place of origin. Piles of mixed plastics, containing different types of plastic, pose a challenge to recycling efforts. Such mixtures often cannot be recycled, leading to their disposal in incinerators rather than being reintroduced into the circulation. Surveys have shown, it would be easier to recycle plastic on farms, especially on farms that generate large amounts of plastic, if the plastic rolls were accompanied by a bag made of the same raw material, in which the used plastics could be collected.

Initial discussions have already been held with the PlastLife project, marking the beginning of a collaborative effort. Ongoing dialogues with stakeholders involved in the agricultural plastic value chain continue to shed light on the needs, challenges, and future prospects of this sector. These insights are gathered through active participation in ongoing discussions and events, such as Finland's Circular

Economy Green Deal and the Plastic Forum. Existing knowledge and best practices have been explored through various EU projects, including MicrAgri, Cicwaste, MINAGRIS, and PAPILLONS. This exploration involves attending both online and in-person sessions, as well as reviewing materials produced by these projects.

The challenges and needs for progress within the plastic value chain have been highlighted in numerous presentations. These include several at Tampere University, meetings with MTK's expert groups (comprising external experts relevant to the topic), such as those focused on environment and land use, climate and biodiversity, and numerous municipal meetings across Finland.

The processing methods for agricultural plastics in the Nordic countries and Estonia have been studied, with a focus on identifying and implementing good practices. For instance, the Swedish pop-up collection system has been considered and discussed in the context of the Finnish model. It appears that elements of this system are being incorporated into the new collection system being introduced in Finland. However, despite these advancements, there is still room for improvement across all countries to enhance the recycling rate.

3.5.2 Household rigid plastic waste collection campaign (Finland)

In Finland the collection rate for packaging plastics in 2022 was approximately 45%. (Sumi oy, 2023) The figure shows that even if recycling processes exist there is still lot to do to engage all citizens in recycling. To increase the knowledge and awareness of the topic several stakeholder engagement activities have been implemented and many of those have been carried out in co-operation with educational organizations. Ekokumppanit has given visiting lectures for Pälkäne school and Hakkari school in Lempäälä. The aim of the lectures was to share information about circular economy and plastics recycling. In spring 2023 a plastic recycling event was held together with vocational school Tredu and Tampere university. 7th grades children from two schools from Viljakkala and Vesilahti visited the event. The event contained lectures and participatory activities for the children. To reach the higher educational levels Ekokumppanit and VTT organized an event for material engineering university students. During the event students visited VTT mechanical recycling laboratory and learned about recycling technologies.

In stakeholder engagement it is sometimes hard to reach the citizens that have no previous interest in environmental sustainability and circular economy. In 2022 a Children toy swap event was organized to promote reuse of plastic items. Citizens could bring their old toys to the event and swap them for other ones. Visitors also had the possibility to listen to circular economy-related presentations. The event got a lot of attention and introduced Tampere citizens to the circular economy in a very practical way. In addition to the swap event, Ekokumppanit and Pirkanmaa waste management company have created a circular economy exhibition that has been on a tour in different libraries. One of the key topics of the exhibition is plastics recycling. Within the exhibition all people visiting the library can get familiar with circular economy and plastic recycling.

4 Conclusions and key learnings

The transition to a circular economy of plastics is a complex and multifaceted challenge. This report provides an in-depth overview of the current state of the circular economy of plastics within the EU and Nordic countries, highlighting several critical areas. It covers optimized collection and logistics, which are essential for ensuring that plastic waste is efficiently gathered and transported for recycling. Additionally, the report emphasizes the importance of boosting recycling rates and increasing the uptake of recycled plastics in new products. Throughout the project, numerous results have been generated, offering valuable insights into effective strategies and practices. Notably, the report presents various circular plastics demonstrations, showcasing practical applications and their outcomes. These demonstrations and their results form the key learnings of the report, offering a roadmap for advancing the circular economy of plastics in the Nordic regions.

The key learnings are:

1. Circular economy initiatives can drive economic growth by creating jobs in waste collection, recycling, and manufacturing with recycled materials. Efforts to increase plastic value chain circularity are driven by regulatory pressure, organizational commitment, and industry competition and collaboration.
2. Circular business models (CBMs) have mainly focused on recycling without altering the core business model. However, new models with inherent circularity are emerging, such as eliminating unnecessary plastic products, reusing plastic items, and repairing equipment by replacing broken plastic parts.
3. A significant barrier to the recyclability and increased recycled content of plastic products is their complex design, including the use of composites and multi-layer packaging. Promoting eco-design with mono-material, single-layer solutions, and design for disassembly should be integrated into procurement procedures to boost demand for recyclable and reusable products. Specifications for the relevant product and plastic type must be established to ensure the recyclability of procured products.
4. Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) is an environmental policy that makes producers responsible for their products' end-of-life management, shifting waste management costs from local governments to the industry and encouraging more recyclable products.
5. The better sorted the plastic materials, the better the recycling output, which refers to all analysed waste streams and is valid for both mechanical and chemical recycling. Therefore, significant efforts towards proper collection and sorting are essential. Many solutions for improving collection and sorting remain unimplemented, likely due to cost concerns. This lack of implementation results in the loss of valuable plastic waste materials.
6. Rigid plastics waste from households is significantly underutilized and there is ample room for improvement. This plastic waste stream typically contains a high proportion of polyolefins, making it highly suitable for both mechanical and chemical recycling technologies. Effective recycling, however, requires thorough sorting of the waste. Currently, automatic sorting facilities for rigid plastics are scarce, leading to a reliance on manual sorting, which increases process costs. Consequently, there is a need to implement new technologies that can efficiently identify and separate plastic items.

7. Regarding agricultural plastics, the most significant need is the construction of a functional and cost-effective recycling system for all types of plastics. For effective recycling, it is essential to advise farms on the proper handling and storage of plastic waste at the source, including how plastics should be cleaned, packed, and stored. Properly processed agricultural plastic serves as an excellent raw material for recycling. However, it is important to ensure that the costs of organizing recycling do not fall solely on the farms.
8. An effective strategy to improve the management of plastics and increase plastic value chain circularity is to raise awareness about the importance and benefits of proper plastic handling. Additionally, measuring the effects of these efforts can provide valuable insights into their effectiveness and guide future initiatives.

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